

PROJECT TITLE: Responsible Open Science for One Health in South Asia-
(REASON- SA)

Summary

Open Science is the measure taken to accelerate responsible conduct of research in scientific advancements, to improve the quality of research, ensure transparency in the sharing of data on open access platforms, and making the data easily accessible to all citizens. (1,2) Although the Open Science movement in research and innovations came into existence a decade ago, the openness of data sharing in One Health is not always executed. (3) The One Health framework is “an integrated unified approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the health of people, animals, and ecosystems”.(4) Due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders (epidemiologists, veterinarians, ecologists, policymakers), the One Health researchers in Asia face constant challenges in evaluating the impact of One Health. On account of the lack of aiding policies and low institutional capacities for One Health in South Asia (5,6), we anticipate a wide range of challenges in One Health. No scientific advancement is without challenge, one such is the One Health framework, which needs close attention to ensure ethics and research integrity in the era of open data sharing. Citizen Science deals with the general public's involvement in scientific research to solve concrete problems in society. Therefore, incorporating both Open Science and Citizen Science into One Health would form a solid basis for ensuring research integrity in One Health research.

The **objectives** of this study are to conduct a scoping review to identify opportunities and challenges in One Health in the realm of Open Science through a scoping review of literature. Next, we aim to explore the perceptions of One Health stakeholders about inequities brought about by Open Science in One Health. Finally, to pinpoint the grey areas and develop a framework to accelerate ethics and research integrity in One Health through Open Science.

This is a non-interventional study with three phases: The first, a scoping review with critical analysis; the second, an online survey **to identify key barriers** that hinder the adoption of open science practices in the One Health research community in South Asia. Based on the analysis of phases 1 and 2, we will develop a framework to incorporate ethics and research integrity through Open Science considerations, into One Health. This will comprehensively facilitate scientific research, by considering the interdependence of science, ethics, and society in the South Asian countries.

Relevance and importance to society

This project is designed in accordance with the objectives of the ROSiE (Responsible Open Science in Europe) project funded by HORIZON 2020. The strategic objectives of ROSiE are to identify ethical and legal issues and new forms of scientific misconduct brought about by Open Science. Second, to analyze them within the ethical and legal frameworks, and integrate ethics and research integrity in Open Science. Besides, the project aligns with the University of Oslo- Strategy 2030, wherein, the project will contribute to sustainable social development, as the outcome of this study will enhance research integrity and ethics in research concerning public health problems. Moreover, it will accelerate society's trust in public health research through community engagement, transparency, and openness in data sharing. Since South Asia is in a nascent stage of implementation of the One Health approach in the realm of Open Science, this study will enhance the One Health researchers and policy-makers to adopt the best practices of the open-data-sharing strategy through Open Science. Thereby contributing to sustainable social development in the region.

Ethical perspectives

Approval for the study will be obtained from the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD). The reference number for the same are attached. The data collection will begin only after obtaining approval from NSD (Ref. no: 631691). As the study involves human participants, we will strictly adhere to all the principles of biomedical research given in the Declaration of Helsinki (DOH- 2013). The research will also be carried out in accordance with recognized ethical standards in research, cf. Section 4 of the Norwegian Act on ethics and integrity in research. All the participants will be given all details regarding the study and adequate time to make a voluntary decision to participate in the study.

References

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